

ASTM D 5528 - MODE I INTERLAMINAR FRACTURE TIGHTNESS OF UNIDIRECTIONAL FIBER-REINFORCED POLYMER MATRIX COMPOSITES
Material CNF s

	Specimen number (included)	Width [mm]	Thickness [mm]
1	1	20.00	4.00
2	2	20.00	4.00
3	3	20.00	4.00
4	4	20.00	4.00
5	5	20.00	4.00
Coefficient of variation	52.70	0.00	0.00
Standard deviation	1.58	0.00	0.00
Maximum	5	20.00	4.00

	Ao [mm]	Maximum Displacement [mm]	Maximum Force [N]
1	40.00	14.6571	62.2552
2	40.00	10.6615	67.8844
3	40.00	11.1695	69.0089
4	40.00	12.4815	66.2327
5	40.00	12.4157	71.9765
Coefficient of variation	0.00	12.59	5.32
Standard deviation	0.00	1.55	3.59
Maximum	40.00	14.6571	71.9765

Force vs. Displacement

Specimen 1 to 5

